

COBALT COPPER ALLOYS ENCAPSULATED BY MoS_2/N -DOPED GRAPHENE NANO-HETEROSTRUCTURES FOR ORR APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a hybrid containing cobalt-copper alloys encapsulated 2D-molybdenum disulfide/nitrogen-doped graphene ($\text{CuCo@2D-MoS}_2/\text{N-Gr}$) is synthesized by a simple thermal treatment and investigated as a catalyst for oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in alkaline solution. Benefiting from the large electrochemical surface area of 2D-MoS_2 and Gr, the highly electrical conductivity of Gr, good synergetic effects between Cu and Co, good contact between MoS_2 and N-Gr, and N-doping effect, the resulting $\text{CuCo@2D-MoS}_2/\text{N-Gr}$ hybrid exhibits high catalytic performance for ORR with positive onset (0.96 V), high current density ($-6 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$), superior stability, and good methanol tolerance compared to the commercial Pt/C catalyst. The $\text{CuCo@2D-MoS}_2/\text{N-Gr}$ hybrid is expected as a promising catalyst material for fuel cell applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, the studies on energy conversion and storage systems with high efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and simple production have been recognized as one of the best solutions for replacing fossil fuels. Among these technologies, fuel cell is considered as a promising approach for converting chemical energies into electrical energy due to its high-energy efficiency, low cost and low air pollution [1]. However, the sluggish oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at cathode of a fuel cell usually hinders its total efficiency for practical application. Thus, the development of efficient electrocatalysts to speed up the kinetic of ORR is necessary [2]. Until now, Pt-based catalysts have been known as a best catalyst toward the ORR; however, the high cost, low chemical stability, easy CO poisoning, and scarcity limit their extensive usage [3]. For this reason, the development of inexpensive metal-based catalysts with long durability, high efficiency, wide potential and eco-friendliness is an urgent requirement. Transition bimetallic nanoparticles possess various advantages, such as abundance, low-cost, high catalytic activity..., thus they have been recognized as an attractive electrocatalysts for ORR [4, 5]. To further enhance the ORR activity, transition nanoparticles could be attached onto highly conductive substrates, such as carbon nanosheets and carbon nanotubes to prevent nanoparticles from agglomeration and extend the surface contact between catalytic materials and reactants. Among promising supporting materials, graphene (Gr), particularly nitrogen (N)-doped Gr, has attracted much attention due to its high conductivity and chemical stability [6]. For example, Yasmin et al. reported the Pd- Mn_2O_3 bimetallic nanoparticles grown on reduced graphene oxide ($\text{rGO/Pd-Mn}_2\text{O}_3$) as highly ORR activity with positive onset and half-wave potential [7]. In another study, Raghavendra et al. demonstrated that the Pd@Au bimetallic nanoparticles supported by reduced graphene oxide was an efficient electrocatalyst towards ORR in comparison with a commercial Pt/C catalyst [8]. Thanh et al. developed a high-performance catalyst for ORR based on CuAg@Ag core-shell nanostructure encapsulated by N-doped graphene [9]. In addition, Mo-based compounds such as Mo_2C , MoN, and MoS_2 were demonstrated to have the catalytic behavior like Pt; therefore, they could be considered as interested electrocatalysts for various electrochemical process. Recently, it was evidenced that the combination of Mo-based compounds and N-Gr could also increase active and stability of

electrocatalysts [10]. Therefore, in this study, we developed a novel electrocatalyst for ORR based on cobalt-copper alloys encapsulated in 2D-molybdenum disulfide/nitrogen-doped graphene heterostructure (CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr). The high performance of the CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr can open a new option for developing effective non-Pt catalyst in fuel cells.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Cobalt (II) nitrate hexahydrate (Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, 99.9%), copper (II) nitrate trihydrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, 99.9%), ammonium tetra-thiomolybdate ((NH₄)₂MoS₄, ≥ 99%), graphite powder, thiourea (NH₂CSNH₂, ≥ 99%), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄, ≥ 99%), nafion solution (5 wt%), hydrogen peroxide solution (H₂O₂, 30%), Pt/C catalyst (20 wt%), methanol (CH₃OH, 99.9%), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 35-37%), and potassium hydroxides (KOH, ≥ 99.5%) were provided from Sigma. Co (USA).

2.2 Preparation for MoS₂ flakes

For the synthesis MoS₂ flakes, 0.5 g of the (NH₄)₂MoS₄ salt was kept in a quartz boat and annealed at 450 °C under 150 sccm flow rate of H₂/Ar (4/6) for 2 h and at 900 °C for 3 h under 150 sccm flow rate of Ar gas.

2.3 Preparation for CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr

In a particular procedure, CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr was synthesized via a specific procedure, in which 100 mL of deionized water containing 0.06 g GO, 0.025 g Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, and 0.025 g Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O were sonication for 1 h. After that, 0.48 g thiourea and 0.01 g (NH₄)₂MoS₄ were slowly added in to the mixture under magnetic stirring for 3 h at room temperature. The mixture was then freeze-dried to obtain a solid product. Finally, the solid product was annealed at 450 °C under flow rate of H₂/Ar (4/6,150 sccm) for 3 h and then at 900 °C for 3 h under Ar (150 sccm) to obtain CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: A schematic illustration for the synthesis of the CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid.

2.4 Electrochemical characterization

The morphology of the as-prepared materials was characterized by FE-SEM on a Supra 40 VP instrument. Insight microstructure of the materials was observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and high-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) through a JEM-2200FS instrument. The crystallinity and phase structure of the materials were investigated by X-ray diffractions (XRD) through a D/Max

2500 V/PC with Cu target ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was conducted by a Theta Probe to identify elemental composition as well as interactions of materials.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphological and structural characterization

The morphology of N-Gr, MoS₂/N-Gr, and CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr were investigated by the FE-SEM. Figure 2a showed the crumples and wrinkles structure of the N-Gr surface, which was attributed to the relatively large amount of the nitrogen doping effect and their interlayer π - π stacking by the thermal process. Meanwhile, the MoS₂/N-Gr exhibited a hierarchical nanostructure due to abundant MoS₂ nanosheets vertically growing on graphene structure (Fig. 2b). In the case of the CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr, Figures 2c and 2d showed the uniform distribution of CuCo NPs homogeneously on the 2D MoS₂/N-Gr sheets, implying the successful fabrication of such nanohybrid.

Figure 2: SEM images of (a) N-Gr; (b) MoS₂/N-Gr; and (c and d) CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid.

Consistent with SEM observations in Figure 2, the morphological characteristics of the N-Gr, MoS₂/N-Gr, and CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid were investigated by TEM and HR-TEM. Figure 3a confirmed the transparent graphene nanosheets. In Figure 3b, it is clearly discerned that the inlaid MoS₂ layer uniformly dispersed on the N-Gr structure, indicating the successful synthesis of 2D MoS₂/N-Gr composite, fully consistent with SEM results. The TEM and HR-TEM images of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr revealed that the CuCo NPs were uniformly deposited on the surface of the MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid (Fig. 3c). The HR-TEM image of the hybrid (Fig. 3d) showed the formation of the CuCo NPs with the size around 32 nm supported on the framework of the 2D MoS₂/N-Gr.

3.2 XRD, Raman and XPS analysis

The crystalline characteristics of GO, N-Gr, and CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr were observed by XRD technique (Fig. 4a). The XRD shows an intense peak at 11.1° corresponding to d(001) plane of the carbon phase. After reduction, there was a new diffraction peak at 26.3° corresponding to d(002) plane of the N-Gr, indicating that the nitrogen has been successfully doped into graphene nanosheets. The

XRD pattern of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid displayed strong diffraction peaks at 32.8°, 39.4°, 50.0°, and 58.6° corresponded to the d(100), d(103), d(105), and d(110) planes, respectively, of the crystalline MoS₂ (PDF 37-1492). The diffraction peaks observed at 43.24°, 50.36°, 73.98°, and 89.74° corresponded to the d(111), d(020), d(022), and d(131) planes, respectively, of the crystalline Co (PDF 901-2949). And peaks at 43.29°, 50.1°, 74.0°, and 89.8° corresponded to the d(111), d(020), d(022), and d(131) planes, respectively, of the crystalline Cu (PDF 710-1265).

Figure 3: TEM images of (a) N-Gr; (b) MoS₂/N-Gr; and (c and d) CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid.

To further investigate the structure of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr, Raman technique was carried out. Figure 4b showed all as-synthesized clearly displayed the D and G bands at 1342.6 and 1583.6 cm⁻¹, respectively, suggesting the presence of Gr in the hybrid. The intensity ratios of the D band to G band of the GO, N-Gr, and CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid was 0.78, 1.03, 1.35, respectively, demonstrating that more disordered structures of graphene in N-Gr and hybrid, due to the nitrogen doping effects. The elemental composition of materials was characterized by XPS spectroscopy. Figure 4c showed that the survey spectrum of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr had C1s, N1s, O1s, Cu2p, Co2p, Mo3d, and S2p binding energy at 285.08, 398.08, 531.08, 993.08, 790.08, 232.08, and 168.08 eV, respectively. In particular, the XPS survey spectrum of the hybrid confirmed the existence of Cu2p, Co2p, Mo3d, and S2p in its structure.

Figure 4. (a) XRD, (b) Raman, (c) XPS of the GO, N-Gr and CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid.

3.3 Electrocatalytic activity towards ORR

The oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) of the synthesized CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid was investigated using CV measurement carried out in 0.1 M KOH solution saturated with N₂ and O₂ gas at a scan rate of 50 mV·s⁻¹ (Fig. 5a). The electrode reveals that the reduction current appeared with a well-defined cathodic peak at 0.92 V in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution, suggesting a good electrocatalytic activity of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr for the ORR. For a comparison, the performance electrocatalytic activities of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr, MoS₂/N-Gr, N-Gr, monometallic hybrid catalysts, and Pt/C commercial (20%) were also studied by linear sweep voltammograms (LSV). Figure 5b showed that the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr owned a significantly higher onset potential (0.96 V) than the other synthesized materials as well as Pt/C. The high catalytic activity of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid was further examined by EIS, which showed a smaller charge-transfer resistance value (35.1 Ω) than that of MoS₂/N-Gr (51.5 Ω), N-Gr (78.1 Ω) and other monometallic hybrid catalysts (Fig. 5c). The durability of the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid was also evaluated by chronoamperometric measurement at 0.86 V (Fig. 5d). After 30, 000 s, the retention of the currents for the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr hybrid was 96.2%, which is higher than Pt/C catalyst.

Figure 5: (a) Cyclic voltammograms of the CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr in N₂ and O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution at a scan rate of 0.05 V·s⁻¹; (b) The LSV curves of N-Gr, MoS₂/N-Gr, Cu@MoS₂/N-Gr, Co@MoS₂/N-Gr, and CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution at rotation speed of 1600 rpm and potential scan rate of 0.01 V·s⁻¹; (d) electrochemical stability for CuCo@2D-MoS₂/N-Gr and Pt/C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, a facile and cost-effective strategy was developed for CuCo NPs encapsulated by 2D hierarchical MoS₂/N-Gr heterostructures. Due to the synergistic effect of excellent catalyst materials and the unique structural features, such a hybrid material exhibited good electrochemical properties, including a comparable catalytic behavior as compared to commercial Pt/C product. In particular, the CuCo@2D MoS₂/N-Gr demonstrated an improved working stability in which the chronoamperometric current density of hybrid remained 96.2 % even after long-term working time of 30,000 s, outperforming Pt/C. Therefore, this hybrid may open a new window for development of cost-efficient material with good performance for fuel cell applications.

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